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Correction: Effect of the formulation and structure of monoglyceride-based gels on the viability of probiotic *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* upon *in vitro* digestion

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Correction for 'Effect of the formulation and structure of monoglyceride-based gels on the viability of probiotic *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* upon *in vitro* digestion' by Sofia Melchior et al., *Food Funct.*, 2021, DOI: 10.1039/D0FO01788D.

The authors regret that the images in Table 2 depicting the visual appearance of the samples were incorrect in the original article. The correct version of Table 2 is given below.

Table 2 Visual appearance, micrographs under normal and polarized light, and pH of binary (B-water and B-milk) and ternary (T-water, T-milk) systems

System	Visual appearance	Micrograph under normal light	Micrograph under polarized light	pH
B-water				5.49 ± 0.01
B-milk				5.51 ± 0.01
T-water				5.19 ± 0.01
T-milk				5.57 ± 0.02

The Royal Society of Chemistry apologises for these errors and any consequent inconvenience to authors and readers.

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